

DESIGN ON A SMALL WIND TURBINE BLADE WITH GLASS/EPOXY AND URETHANE FOAM SANDWICH COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: This study proposes a development for the 1-kW class small wind turbine system, which is applicable to relatively low wind speed region like Korea and has the variable pitch control mechanism. In the aerodynamic design of the wind turbine blade, parametric studies were carried out to determine an optimum aerodynamic configuration which is not only more efficient at low wind speed but whose diameter is not much larger than similar class other blades. A light composite structure, which can endure effectively various loads, was newly designed. In order to evaluate the structural design of the composite blade, the structural analysis was performed by the finite element method. Moreover both structural safety and aerodynamic performance were verified through the prototype test.

KEYWORDS: Small Wind Turbine System, Aerodynamic Design, Structural Design, Prototype Test

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the trend of the wind turbine system development has become much larger scale over several MW class. However, because the small-scale wind turbine system has some advantages, which someone can build personally it with low cost as well as experience energy save effect, it has been continuously developed.

Currently, because most commercialized small scale wind turbine systems have been designed with the rated wind speed more than 12m/s, they show great reduction of aerodynamic efficiency at the low wind speed region like Korea. A small-scale wind turbine blade for low wind speed region, was aerodynamically designed. A specific proper airfoil at low wind speed was selected, and the optimal aerodynamic design was derived through the parametric study on linear chord distribution and blade angle design with maximum lift-drag ratios.

In structural design, the blade uses Glass/Epoxy composite and Urethane foam materials, and its structure adapts the skin/spar/foam sandwich style. Moreover, in order to obtain practical material properties, some specimens with same manufacturing process were tested. In order to perform the structural analysis, a finite element code, NISA II, was used. In this analysis, linear static stress analysis, eigenvalue analysis and buckling analysis were carried out. Finally, the structural safety and the aerodynamic performance were confirmed through the test with the prototype blade made by hand lay-up manufacturing process.

AERODYNAMIC DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

According to the vortex theory of Glauert, the rotational speed of the wind flow relative to the

blade rises to $\omega + \Omega$ at downstream of the rotor, and the angular velocity of the air flow in the plane of the rotor with respect to the blades can be expressed as,

$$\omega + \frac{\Omega}{2} = \left(\frac{1+h}{2}\right)\omega \quad (1)$$

where, Ω is increasing rotational angular speed due to vortices, ω is blade rotational angular speed, and h has the relationship of $(\omega + \Omega = h\omega)$.

The axial speed through the rotor can be written as,

$$V = \frac{V_1 + V_2}{2} = \frac{1+k}{2}V_1 \quad (2)$$

where, V_1, V_2 are axial velocities at upstream and downstream of the plane of the rotor, and k is axial velocity ratio with the relationship of $(V_2 = kV_1)$.

Therefore the inclination angle and relative wind speed at a radius are then given in the rotor plane by the following equations.

$$\begin{cases} \cot I = \frac{U'}{V} = \frac{\omega r}{V_1} \frac{1+h}{1+k} = \lambda \frac{1+h}{1+k} = \lambda_e \\ \overline{W} = \frac{V_1(1+k)}{2 \sin I} = \frac{\omega r(1+h)}{2 \cos I} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where, U is blade rotational speed, λ is blade tip speed ratio and I is inclination angle in the rotor plane. On the other hand, according to the blade elementary theory and the momentum theory, the blade aerodynamic load can be expressed as,

$$C_l b l = \frac{8\pi r(1-k)\sin^2 I \cos \varepsilon}{(1+k)\cos(I-\varepsilon)} \quad C_d b l = \frac{4\pi r(h-1)\sin 2I \cos \varepsilon}{(h+1)\sin(I-\varepsilon)} \quad (4)$$

where, C_l is lift coefficient of the used airfoil at radius r , b is number of blades, l is chord length and ε means $\tan^{-1}(C_d / C_l)$

And the local power coefficient at radius r can be expressed by the function of rotational angular speed ratio and axial velocity ratio as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} C_p &\equiv \frac{dP_\omega}{\rho \pi r dr V_1^3} = \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{V_1^2} (1+k)(h-1) \\ &= \lambda^2 (1+k)(h-1) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In order to find rotational angular speed ratio and axial velocity ratio, the following relationship can be defined as,

$$G \equiv (1-k)/(1+k), E \equiv (h-1)/(h+1) \quad (6)$$

If we use equation (3) and (4), the following relationship can be obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{G}{E} &= \frac{(1-k)(h+1)}{(h-1)(1+k)} = \cot(I-\varepsilon) \cot I \\ &= \frac{\lambda(h+1) + (1+k) \tan \varepsilon}{(1+k) - \lambda(1+h) \tan \varepsilon} \cdot \lambda \frac{1+h}{1+k} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Therefore the relationship between rotational angular speed ratio and axial velocity ratio can be finally expressed by,

$$h = \frac{-\tan \varepsilon + \sqrt{\tan^2 \varepsilon + 2\lambda k \tan \varepsilon + \lambda^2 + (1-k^2)}}{\lambda} \quad (8)$$

If we find k_{opt} value to satisfy the condition of $\frac{dC_p}{dk} = 0$, the optimum rotational angular speed ratio, inclination angle, blade load and local power coefficient can be calculated [1].

Characteristic of Airfoil

In this study, the airfoil of FFA-W3-211, which has relatively high stall angle of attack, maximum lift coefficient and maximum lift-drag ration, and very effective for structural strength due to relatively thick, was selected for the design purpose. Fig. 1 shows the airfoil configuration and aerodynamic characteristics [2].

Fig. 1: Airfoil shape and aerodynamic characteristics for FFA-W3-211

Rated Wind Speed

The blade diameter of the wind turbine system can be approximately obtained from the equation (8) and (9) on the rated power. Therefore it is acceptable for keeping adequate length at the low wind speed that the rated wind speed to decide the blade radius was determined at 8 m/s.

$$P_{max} = 0.37AV^3 \quad (9)$$

where, P_{max} is maximum power by Betz theory, A is Swept area and V is Rated wind speed. Therefore, we can obtain the following relationship to determine the blade diameter, approximately.

$$P = 0.2D^2V^3 \quad (10)$$

Blade Design

There are several methods to design aerodynamically the blade such as chord length and twist angle. Fig. 2 shows comparison between design results using maximum inclination angle design method and them using the linear chord length distribution method with the taper ratio of 0.3. From the Fig. 2, it was found that the maximum inclination angle design method was more effective method because of reduction of the chord length. Specification of the finally designed blade is shown in Table 1. Fig. 3 shows the designed aerodynamic configuration.

Fig. 2: Distribution of the chord

Table 1: Aerodynamic design results

Rated power	1 kW	Blade number	3
Cut in wind speed	3.0 m/s	Rotor diameter	3.42 m
Rated wind speed	8.0 m/s	Aerodynamic profile	FFA-W3-211
Cut out wind speed	25 m/s	Blade root chord	253mm
Design tip speed ratio	6.0	Blade tip chord	73mm
Rated RPM	268 rpm	Blade total twist	20.23 deg.

Fig. 3: Aerodynamic shape of designed blade

Aerodynamic Analysis

Fig. 4 shows power variation at each wind speed depending on the blade rotational speed. In this fig., we can find the specific rotational speed with maximum power at each wind speed. Fig. 5 shows power variation versus wind speed variation at optimum rotational speed.

Fig. 4: Aerodynamic power vs. RPM

Fig. 5: Aerodynamic power vs. wind speed

STRUCTURAL DESIGN

Design Load

Loads acted on the wind turbine blade are divided into major aerodynamic loads and subsidiary loads due to gravity, motion and centrifugal force in rotating, ice, temperature and humidity effects, faults of the wind turbine system, braking, etc. in service [3]. It is very difficult to analysis all these loads because they are related to each other. Therefore, the aerodynamic loads mainly acted on the blade are analyzed here. Table 2 shows the load cases for the blade design. The maximum load case is the load case II, that is the rated wind speed condition with the gust wind and variation of the wind direction. Therefore, the structural design was carried out based on the load case II. Fig. 6 shows the flapwise moment distribution of the design load case.

Table 2: Load case for structural design

Load case	Case I	Case II	Case III
Reference wind speed	8.0 m/s	25.0 m/s	55.0 m/s
Gust condition(± 20 m/s, 40°)	Without gust	With gust	Storm
Rotational speed	268 rpm	300 rpm	Stop

Fig. 6: Flap wise moment diagram for load case II

Fig. 7 shows the representative sectional view of the blade profile structure. The bending force is kept by the spar flange layered by plies angle of $0^\circ/90^\circ$. The torsion is kept by the upper and lower skins manufactured with the angle ply ($\pm 45^\circ$). In order to reduce the weight and to strengthen both the dynamic stability and the buckling strength, the sandwich structure with the urethane foam core was used. Moreover, the compression side spar is slightly thicker than the tension side spar. The main spar flange is extended to the tip of the blade, but its thickness is gradually reduced along the spar to reduce the weight. The structural configuration for the rotor blade is determined by trial and error.

Fig. 7: Section view of the blade structure

Specimen Test

Generally, the strength of the open molded composite is lower than the autoclave molded composite. And most of the literature data of composite materials are based on the autoclave molded specimen test. Therefore the specimen tests for open molded glass/epoxy composite are requested. Fig. 8 shows the test specimen and Table 3 shows the specimen test results.

Fig. 8: Compression test specimen [ASTM D695] & Tensile test specimen [ASTM D638]

Table 3 : Mechanical properties of materials used in the present blades design

Property \ Material	Glass/Epoxy Fabric	Polyurethane Foam
E_1 (N/mm ²)	10500	60.86
E_2 (N/mm ²)	10500	59.86
G_{12} (N/mm ²)	1450	19.18
ν	0.27	0.2
X_t (N/mm ²)	283.9	2.63
X_c (N/mm ²)	184.6	1.41
Y_t (N/mm ²)	283.9	2.49
Y_c (N/mm ²)	184.6	1.41
S (N/mm ²)	15.0	0.71
ρ (g/cm ³)	1.705	0.1197
Ply thickness (mm)	0.25	12.5

Structural Analysis

The finite element program used for structural analysis is a commercial code NISA II and the post processing program for displaying the output is DISPLAY III. The element types used for the analysis are the 3-D composite shell element and the number of total elements is 960. Generally, failure is governed by directional material strengths rather than principal stress or strains. Intra-lamina failure criterion used for this design are both the Maximum Stress Failure Criterion [4] and the Tasi-Wu failure criterion .

Linear Static Analysis

According to analysis results, the total weight of the blade is calculated to be 3.16 kg. By the failure criterion the minimum safety factor was 2.6 and confirmed safe. Table 4 shows the

stress analyses results for three load cases. Fig. 9 shows the stress distribution at the first ply of the spar flange for the load case II.

Table 4: Structural analysis results

Case of analysis		Case I	Case II	Case III
Max. Stress[Mpa]	Ten.	13.9	38.5	33.3
	Com.	10.8	31.1	29.4
Max. Disp. [mm]		52.84	151.0	123.2
Max. stress failure criterion	$S_{xx}/\sigma_{xx}allow$	0.053	0.165	0.162
	$S_{yy}/\sigma_{yy}allow$	0.027	0.089	0.095
	$S_{xy}/\sigma_{xy}allow$	0.125	0.384	0.364
Tsai-Wu failure criterion		0.035	0.217	0.205

Fig. 9: Stress analysis result of load case II

Eigenvalue Analysis

Dynamic effects can be substantial in a wind turbine system because of the periodic nature of its aerodynamic loading. As a result, the design process must depend on determination of the dynamic characteristics of the rotating structure. In this study, modal analysis is performed by the finite element method. Fig. 10 shows the results of modal analysis for natural frequencies such as the first flap-wise and chord-wise bending modes, displayed in a frequency plot called a Campbell diagram. Rays of origin are plots of integer multiples of the rotational frequency. In a rotating structure, excitation loading occurs normally at these multiple frequencies, often abbreviated 1p(once per rotation), 3p, 6p, etc. Resonance is a phenomenon, which occurs in a structure when the frequency of periodic loading or excitation equals or nearly equals one of the modal frequencies of the structure. Thus, as shown in Fig. 10, because there are no intersections of a radial line and a modal frequency line, there may not be any resonance between the blade and excitation loadings.

Fig.10: Campbell diagram

Buckling Analysis

In this study, the buckling analysis is done by the finite element method. The finite element model for buckling analysis is same as the static analysis model under loading in the load case 2. Fig. 11 shows buckling load factors for the first buckling mode location of the blade. The buckling load factor means the ratio of the buckling load to the applied load. Generally, the most important buckling mode is the first mode, i.e. the critical mode. In this study the minimum buckling load factor was 2.18 and was confirmed safe from buckling.

Fig. 11: First buckling mode shape & load factor

FULL SCALE STRUCTURAL TEST

Eigenvalue Test

In order to measure the natural frequency of the blade, it was impacted by the impulse hammer. At that time, the sampling frequency was 500 Hz. The obtained strain data were analyzed by FFT technique of MATLAB program. Fig. 12 shows the obtained strain data and the FFT analysis result. Table 5 shows the measured and predicted natural frequencies. As shown in the table, the predicted values are in good agreement with the measured values.

Table 5: Comparison between measured and predicted natural frequencies

Mode shape	Analysis results	Test results
First flap mode	12.81 Hz	11.72 Hz
First lead-lag mode	23.25 Hz	21.09 Hz
Second flap mode	42.77 Hz	41.31 Hz

Fig. 12: Eigenvalue test results

Static Test

The manufactured prototype blade was set on the test rig and loaded at 0.9m, 1.2m and 1.6m stations of the blade by sandbags, and strains and deflections of the blade were measured. As a load for the static test, the load case II was applied. The load case II has the aerodynamic load at the cutout wind speed in practical operation including gust. In order to simulate the aerodynamics load, the three-point loading method was applied. Fig. 13 shows load values and loading points in flapwise direction for the static strength test.

A prototype blade for the static strength test was tested, and used for comparison with the analyzed model. During the test until the maximum loading, there was no failure such as catastrophic failure, local failure, de-bonding, de-lamination, local buckling, etc. Table 6 shows both measured and predicted results for the stress of the 0.2 r/R station and the tip deflection. Prediction from the model is in good agreement with the measured values indicating that, at least, the structural construction of the blade was reasonably modeled.

Fig. 13: Static strength test load

Table 6: Comparison between the linear static analysis results and the static test results

Item	Analysis results	Test results
Tip displacement	131 mm	150 mm
Stress at 0.2 r/R station	+29.7 Mpa -21.8 Mpa	+27.0 Mpa -16.9 Mpa

AERODYNAMIC PERFORMANCE TEST

Aerodynamic test was performed to prove the performance of the designed blade. As shown in the fig. 14, the blade pitch angle can be changed while the blades are testing. Fig. 15 shows the testing wind turbine system and the data storage system.

The calculated values are electrical power including the 80% of efficiency. Moreover, in the calculation it is assumed that the power would be regulated after approaching the rated power. in case of the blade pitch angle is 0° , it was found that the test results are good agreed with the analysis results, and the mechanical efficiency of the test equipment is about 90%. However in case of the blade pitch angle is not 0° , the test values are a little bit lower than the calculated value. It seems that the blades are in the face of the partial stall.

In case of the blade pitch angle of -6° , the wind turbine can not be started at low wind speeds less than 4 m/s. As a result it is found that the starting characteristics of the blades could be improved by proper blade pitch control.

Fig. 14: Hub assembly part with torque measuring device and pitch control mechanism

Fig. 15: Testing wind turbine system and data acquisition system

CONCLUSION

In this study, an optimum aerodynamic configuration of the small wind turbine blade was proposed by parametric studies. From the aerodynamic design result, the designed blade has about 1kW power at the rated wind speed of 8 m/s. And it is more efficient at low wind speed and its diameter is not much longer than similar class other blades. From the test results, it is found that the starting characteristics of the blades can be improved by proper blade pitch control and the test values are good agreed with the calculated values. In structural design, a light composite structure, which can endure effectively various loads, was designed. In order to evaluate the designed structure, the structural analysis was performed by the finite element method. According to linear static structural analysis, it is confirmed that the safety factor of the structure has about 2.6 at the maximum operation wind speed of 25 m/s. In order to keep the safety for the extreme condition, it was analyzed in storm condition of 55m/s. Through this analysis it is confirmed the safety factor is 2.75. Through the eigenvalue analysis, it is obtained that the natural frequencies are the 1st flap mode of 12.81 Hz and the 1st lead-lag mode of 23.25 Hz. It is found that the blade has no resonance in operating range. For the buckling analysis, it has a sufficient buckling load factor of 2.18 due to adapting the foam sandwich structure. The full-scale static structural test was performed under the simulated aerodynamic loads. From the experimental results, it is found that the designed blade has the structural integrity. Furthermore the measured results are well agreed with the analytical results such as deflections, strains and natural frequency.

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